

THE IMPORTANCE OF FINE ARTS IN AESTHETIC EDUCATION

Fargona Davlat Universiteti San'atshunoslik fakulteti Tasviriy san'at va Muhandislik grafikasi yonalishi 18.23 guruh talabasi Isroilova Muqaddas

Annotation. Fine art is the expression on paper of the beauty of being. The importance of this art in the human psyche, but also in its aesthetic views, is incomparable. This article explains in detail the importance of fine arts in aesthetic education.

Keywords: fine arts, artist, landscape, nature, human psyche, aesthetic education, etc.

Fine art is an elegant art form that combines painting, sculpture, and graphics; reflects reality in its easily perceived spatial forms in visual images. Types of fine arts, depending on their characteristics, create a sense of objective existence of the real being - size, color, space, as well as the material form of the object and the radiant environment, movement and change, moving from the emotional specificity of the image to illusionism. can be switched. Fine art not only depicts what can be seen, but also expands the possibilities of ideological mastery of the world by reflecting the temporal development of events, its part (fabula), free storytelling, and dynamic movements. Fine art also illuminates a person's mental image, his or her interactions with others, and the psychological and emotional content of the visual state. Sometimes it creates images that do not exist, that are the product of the artist's imagination. Reflects different periods in human history. Not only the emotional state of the period, but also its ideological essence, political, philosophical, aesthetic and ethical ideas become the content of Fine Arts. The visualization of fine arts allows the artist to express his or her attitude to a particular event in life at a high level; therefore, as an active form of knowledge of life, it plays an important role in the social life of society, in the decision-making of the public consciousness of a particular system. It forms social consciousness as one of the forms of knowing the world and also plays an important role as a form of expression of the people's dreams. In modern conditions, it is seen as part of a general struggle.

Fine arts classes in general education schools are one of the main means of aesthetic education and play an important role in the spiritual development of students. In fine arts classes, students acquire the basics of scientific knowledge, master the being, which is effective in educating them ideologically, mentally, morally, aesthetically. Fine arts classes play a key role in shaping students' spiritual outlook and ideological convictions. It develops thinking skills, visual memory, creative imagination, artistic taste, aesthetic sense. Each type of art lessons taught at school (drawing on the object itself, decorative painting, drawing on the topic, conversation about fine arts) helps to develop students' creative abilities, the formation of their worldview, that is, it perfects the person in every way. One of the main tasks of the fine arts is to educate students in aesthetics, especially art. Aesthetic education is the development of students' ability to fully understand the beauty of life, nature, art and society. Beauty influences people's minds, hearts and wills and enriches their spiritual worldview.

The role of aesthetics in the creative activities of human beings is enormous. An aesthetic approach to life is the basis of inspiration and helps to turn work into a source of joy and spiritual pleasure. In the process of aesthetic education, people's views, feelings and tastes are formed. This formation is closely connected with the ideological and political upbringing, the development of creative thinking. One of the main tasks of our schools today is not only to form in students the need and ability to creatively master the being, but also to instill in them a sense of reconstruction of the being on the basis of the laws of beauty. Everyone in our society should be able to see and understand beauty and elegance, no matter what field they work in. In order to educate students aesthetically, the teacher shows them the beauty of nature, the diversity of forms. The beauty of nature, the indescribable color combinations that bring joy and excitement to children, will remain in their minds for a long time. Children will be more interested in nature by drawing pictures of landscapes, tree branches, leaves, and flowers, and by studying their unique features. Classes like these help children see the world more broadly and comprehensively, as well as broaden their horizons and gain a

clearer and more complete understanding of things. In drawing, children carefully study the shape, proportions, spatial position, color, and hunger ratios of objects.

Visual arts activities develop students' visual perception. By the development of visual perception, we mean the ability to observe purposefully, that is, to compare things and events, to identify their differences and commonalities, and to classify things in terms of shape and appearance. Research shows that people visualize more than 90% of all the information they receive from the outside. This shows that the role of the eye in people's lives is unique and that the possibilities of the eye need to be explored. At school, fine arts are more important than other subjects in the development of visual memory and its potential. From this point of view, the role of fine arts in people's lives becomes clearer. Our schools are based on secular education and adhere to didactic principles that can create the pedagogical conditions for easy, concise, well-grounded teaching of any subject. These principles are: scientific, coherent, educative, systematic, consistent, consciously active, demonstrative, creative, the integration of theory and practice, and new teaching materials, from the interdependent teaching of academic disciplines.

A number of educational and pedagogical tasks are performed through the teaching of fine arts. The process of accomplishing these tasks, in turn, allows students to develop their thinking, generalize and deepen their understanding of the environment. On this basis, a materialist worldview is formed in children. The teaching of fine arts in school aims to show in detail what opportunities people learn from realistic drawing. Explain to students that drawing can be used in any job, in any profession. For example: the formation of the ability to draw in humans before writing (images on primitive rocks), the current use of visual activity in the explanation of other sciences, theater, cinema, cartoons, architecture, machinery, toys, design of teaching aids, artistic design of books, we can observe its application in many other areas of room interior design and production. One of the main practical tasks of art in school is to equip students with realistic drawing techniques. To do this, the teacher teaches students how to handle drawing tools, how to draw straight and curved lines, and how to draw three-

dimensional objects in a plane. As the teacher sets himself the task of developing students' creative abilities, the teacher will need to develop the right methodology for working with children. An important factor in improving the quality and effectiveness of education in all areas (types of activities) of fine arts education is the analysis of errors in the work of students in the pedagogical activity of a teacher of fine arts and the appropriate methodological direction and assistance. . Also, the classification of shortcomings by type of activity, genre allows you to choose the right methodology to address the existing shortcomings. One of the elementary errors observed in students' work is that they do not follow the laws of perspective in their landscape, not only the size of the detail away from the point of view of the law of linear perspective is reduced, but also the colors become more general and accurate. Allows for a holistic depiction of details in the middle and background. It is impossible to create an accurate landscape image without considering these requirements.

Orientation of the teacher of fine arts in the process of formation of landscape skills in students, the creative task of directing students to the correct determination of the status of the landscape depicted in the methodology; it is recommended to select the content accordingly. Only then, in the development of a landscape in a certain position, for example, in a lyrical mood (early morning, bright day, quiet evening, sunset, etc.), special details are used in comparison with other landscape compositions. It is recommended that the teacher explain these factors of landscape work through the reproduction of works of fine art in the genre of landscape - illustrative materials created by professional artists and the analysis of artistic means used by the artist through questions and answers with students. that is, it is possible to develop students' practical and visual competencies in landscape work through the formation of skills to apply the practical application in conjunction with the theoretical basis.

References:

1. Sultonov X. E. “Rangtasvir” (Akvarda naturmort ishlash, o’quv qo’llanma T.:“VNESHINVESTROM” MChJ, 2019.
2. B.N. Oripov. Tasviriy san’atni o’qitishning zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyasi, didaktikasi va metodikasi.(o’quv-metodik qo’llanma) Toshkent - «ILM ZIYO» – 2013.
3. Sobirov S.T. “IMPORTANCE OF ILLUSTRATIONS FOR PERCEPTION OF CONTENT OF THE BOOK”. European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences. Volume 8 Number 4, 2020 Part II ISSN 2056-5852. 98-101
4. Sobirov S.T. “SOME FACTORS THAT IMPEDE THE DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' CREATIVE ABILITIES IN FINE ART CLASSES”. Asian Journal of Research № 1-3, 2020, ISSN 2433-202x. 2020 yil. 214-218
5. Султанов Х. Э, Худайбердиев П.У, Собиров С.Т. “Непрерывное образование в Узбекистане как требование времени”. МОЛОДОЙ УЧЁНЫЙ ИЛМИЙ журналининг 2017 йил № 3 сони. 385-388